

On Degree-Distance index of a graph

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Abstract

In this article, we give sufficient conditions for the Hamiltonian and graphical properties of graphs in the terms of degree-distance index. The degree distance index of the graph is defined as the $S(G) = \sum_{u,v \in V(G)} (d(u) + d(v))d_G(u, v)$ where $d(u)$ is the degree of the vertex in a graph and $d_G(u, v)$ is the distance between the vertices u and v in the graph G .

Keyword: Degree distance index, Topological index, Hamiltonian Properties.

1 Introduction

In this paper, we are concerned with a topological invariant of a molecular graph called the Degree distance index. Let G be a connected graph of order n and size m . Let $V(G)$ be the vertex set of G . We use $d_G(u, v)$ to denote the distance between vertices u and v of the graph G , and $d(u)$ is used to denote the degree of the vertex u of the graph. Let K_n denote the complete graph on n vertices. Then the Degree distance index (or degree distance) of G is defined as:

$$S(G) = \sum_{u,v \in V(G)} (d(u) + d(v))d_G(u, v) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{u \in V(G)} \sum_{v \in V(G)} (d(u) + d(v))d_G(u, v)$$

Dobrynin and Kochetova [10] and Gutman [11] independently studied the degree distance sum of a graph. The same was studied by Tomescu [22], Tomescu [22] and Bucicovschi and Cioab [7]. A related concept studied earlier for the chemical applications called "Molecular topological index" MTI by H. P. Schultz in 1989 is defined as follows [19]: Let G be a graph with labeled vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n . Then

$$MTI(G) = \sum_{i=1}^n [v(A + D)]_i$$

where A and D are adjacency and distance matrices of G and $v = (d(v_1), d(v_2), \dots, d(v_n))$. It can be easily seen from [11] that $MTI(G) = M_1(G) + S(G)$, where $M_1(G)$ is first Zagrab index and $S(G)$ is degree distance index.

A connected graph is said to be traceable (or Hamiltonian) if it has a Hamiltonian path (or cycle). A path (or cycle) is said to be a Hamiltonian path (or cycle) if it traverses through all vertices exactly once. A graph is said to be Hamiltonian-connected if it has a Hamiltonian path between every pair of vertices. A graph is said to be k -connected if it remains connected by removing fewer than k vertices. A graph on n vertices is k -edge Hamiltonian if every path of length not exceeding k , $1 \leq k \leq n - 2$, is contained in a Hamiltonian cycle. The graph G is called k -path coverable if $V(G)$ can be covered by k or fewer than k vertex disjoint paths, obviously 1-path coverable is traceable. For a

graph G , if $G[V - X]$ is Hamiltonian for all $|X| \leq k$, we call G to be k -Hamiltonian. In particular, 0-Hamiltonian is same as Hamiltonian. For other undefined graph-theoretic notations and terminology, the reader may refer to [6].

The problem of finding a Hamiltonian cycle is NP-complete as reported in [14]. In 2013, Yang [23] studied the Hamiltonian path in terms of the Wiener index and extended it to the Hamiltonian graph [18]. In the same year, Hua [12] discussed sufficient conditions for traceability in terms of the Harary index. Further, sufficient conditions for k -connected, β -deficient, and Hamiltonian cycle in terms of the first Zagreb index are studied in [2]. Also, An [3] studied graph properties based on reciprocal degree distance and An [1] discussed sufficient conditions for Hamiltonian-connectedness in terms of the first Zagreb index and reciprocal distance. In [20], the author(s) described sufficient conditions for k -edge Hamiltonian, k -path coverable, traceable, and Hamilton-connected graphs in terms of the forgotten index. In [13], author(s) studied sufficient conditions for Hamiltonicity with respect to the Wiener index, hyper-Wiener index, and Harary index. The Hamiltonian and graphical properties in terms of the eccentricity-based topological index are studied in [17, 24].

In this article, we explore sufficient conditions for the Hamiltonian path, Hamiltonian cycle, Hamiltonian-connected, and k -connected graphs in terms of the Degree distance index. The paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, we give some useful propositions which are needed in subsequent sections. In Section 3, we present the results and proofs of this paper.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we will introduce four-degree conditions. In the following propositions, we suppose that the graph satisfies the degree sequence $\pi = (d_1 \leq d_2 \leq \dots \leq d_n)$ condition.

Proposition1. [9] Let G be a graph of order $n \geq 3$ having degree sequence π . If

$$d_i \leq i - 1 \leq \frac{1}{2}(n - 1) \Rightarrow d_{n-i} \geq n - i - 1$$

then G is traceable.

Proposition2. [9] Let G be a graph of order $n \geq 3$ having degree sequence π . If

$$d_i \leq i < \frac{n}{2} \Rightarrow d_{n-i} \geq n - i$$

then G is Hamiltonian.

Proposition3. [8] Let G be a graph of order $n \geq 3$ having degree sequence π . If

$$d_{i-1} \leq i \Rightarrow d_{n-i} \geq n - i + 1, \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2}$$

then G is Hamiltonian connected.

Proposition4. [4] Let G be a graph of order $n \geq 4$ having degree sequence π . If

$$d_i \leq i + k - 2 \Rightarrow d_{n-k+1} \geq n - i, \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{1}{2}(n - k + 1)$$

then G is k -connected.

Proposition 5. [15] Let G be a graph with degree sequence π and $n \geq 3$ and $0 \leq k \leq n - 3$. If

$$d_{i-k} \leq i \Rightarrow d_{n-i} \geq n - i + k, \text{ for } k + 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n + k}{2}$$

then π is k -edge Hamiltonian.

Proposition 6. [9] Let G be graph with degree sequence π and $0 \leq k \leq n - 3$. If

$$d_i \leq i + k \Rightarrow d_{n-i-k} \geq n - i, \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{1}{2}(n - k)$$

then G is k - Hamiltonian.

Proposition 7. [5, 16] If $k \geq 1$ and the degree sequence π of G satisfies

$$d_{i+k} \leq i \rightarrow d_{n-i} \geq n - i - k, \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{1}{2}(n - k)$$

then G is k -path coverable.

Define a graph G_4 as follows: A graph whose set of vertices has partition $A \cup B \cup C \cup D$ such that $|A| = |C| = k$ and $|B| = |D| = m - k$ and whose edges connect each vertex

$u \in A \cup B$ to each vertex $v \in C \cup D$ except when $u \in A$ and $v \in D$.

Proposition 8. [9] Let G be a bipartite graph with vertices (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n) and (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n) such that $d(u_1) \leq d(u_2) \leq \dots \leq d(u_n)$ and $d(v_1) \leq d(v_2) \leq \dots \leq d(v_n)$ and

$$d(u_k) \leq k < n \rightarrow d(v_{n-k}) \geq n - k + 1$$

Then G is either Hamiltonian or G_4 .

3 Degree distance index and Hamiltonicity

This section gives sufficient conditions for a graph to be traceable, Hamiltonian, Hamiltonian-connected, k -connected graphs, k -path coverable, k -Hamiltonian, k -edge Hamiltonian in terms of Degree distance index. Further, we give sufficient condition for bipartite graph to be Hamiltonian in terms of Degree distance index.

Let G be a connected graph, and $S(G)$ denotes the Degree distance index of G : For a vertex v of G , define $D(v) = \sum_{u \in G} d_G(v, u)$ and $D'(v) = d(v)D(v)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} S(G) &= \sum_{v \in G} D'(v) \\ &= \sum_{v \in G} d(v)D(v) \\ &\leq \sum_{v \in G} d(v)[d(v) + (n-1-d(v))(n-1-d(v))] \quad (1) \\ &= (n-1)^2 \sum_{v \in G} d(v) - (2n-3) \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^2 + \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^3 \end{aligned}$$

We now have the following:

Theorem 1. Let G be a connected graph of order $n \geq 5$ and size m . If

$$S(G) \geq 2n^4 - 12n^3 + 27n^2 - 27n + 10 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n}4m^2$$

then G is traceable.

Proof. Suppose that G is not traceable, then by Proposition 1 and Equation1, the Degree distance index of G :

$$\begin{aligned} S(G) &\leq (n-1)^2 \sum_{v \in G} d(v) + \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^3 - (2n-3) \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^2 \\ &\leq (n-1)^2 \sum_{v \in G} d(v) + \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^3 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} \left(\sum_{v \in G} d(v) \right)^2 \\ &\leq (n-1)^2 [k(k-1) + (n-2k+1)(n-k-1) + (k-1)(n-1)] \\ &\quad + [k(k-1)^3 + (n-2k+1)(n-k-1)^3 + (k-1)(n-1)^3] \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &= (n-1)^2 [3k^2 - (2n+1)k + n^2 - n] + [3k^4 - (7n-2)k^3 + (9n^2 - 12n + 6)k^2 \\ &\quad - (4n^3 - 4n^2 + 3)k + n^4 - 3n^3 + 3n^2 - n] - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &= 3k^4 - (7n-2)k^3 + (12n^2 - 18n + 9)k^2 - (6n^3 - 9n^2 + 4)k \\ &\quad + 2n^4 - 6n^3 + 6n^2 - 2n - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &= 2n^4 - 12n^3 + 27n^2 - 27n + 10 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &\quad + (k-1)[3k^3 - (7n-5)k^2 + (12n^2 - 25n + 14)k - 6n^3 + 21n^2 - 25n + 10] \end{aligned}$$

Combining with the condition of the Theorem 1, we know that $(k-1)[3k^3 - (7n-5)k^2 + (12n^2 - 25n + 14)k - 6n^3 + 21n^2 - 25n + 10] \geq 0$. Since G is connected and $k \geq d_k + 1 \geq 2$. Let $q(x) = 3x^3 - (7n-5)k^2 + (12n^2 - 25n + 14)x - 6n^3 + 21n^2 - 25n + 10$. Since k is an integer we have $2 \leq k \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$ is equivalent to $k \leq \frac{n}{2}$. So what follows we assume that $k \leq \frac{n}{2}$

The first derivative of $q(x)$ is $q'(x) = 9x^2 - 2(7n-5)x + (12n^2 - 25n + 14)$ and the discriminant Δ of $q'(x) = 0$ is $\Delta = 4(7n-5)^2 - 36(12n^2 - 25n + 14) = -4(59n^2 - 155n + 101) < 0 \forall n \geq 2$. Therefore $q'(x) > 0$ and $q(x)$ is strictly increasing in the interval of $[2, \frac{n}{2}]$. Hence $\max(q(x))$ is obtained at the right endpoint of the interval $[2, \frac{n}{2}]$. We consider

the parity of n . If n is even then

$$\max(q(x)) = q\left(\frac{n}{2}\right) = -\frac{1}{8}n(n(11n - 78) + 144) + 10 < 0, \forall n \geq 5.$$

If n is odd then

$$\max(q(x)) = q\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right) = -\frac{1}{8}(n-1)(n(11n - 38) + 31) < 0, \forall n \geq 3.$$

Therefore $\max(q(x)) < 0 \forall n \geq 5$. Then $S(G) \leq 2n^4 - 12n^3 + 27n^2 - 27n + 10 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n}4m^2$.

Thus proof is complete \square

Theorem 2. Let G be a connected graph of order $n \geq 12$ and size m . If

$$S(G) \geq 2n^4 - 18n^3 + 82n^2 - 162n + 136 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n}4m^2$$

then G is Hamiltonian.

Proof. Suppose that G is not Hamiltonian, then by Proposition 2 and Equation 1, the Degree distance index of G :

$$\begin{aligned} S(G) &\leq (n-1)^2 \sum_{v \in G} d(v) + \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^3 - (2n-3) \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^2 \\ &\leq (n-1)^2 \sum_{v \in G} d(v) + \sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^3 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} \left(\sum_{v \in G} (d(v))^2 \right) \\ &\leq (n-1)^2 [k^2 + (n-2k)(n-k-1) + k(n-1)] \\ &\quad + [k^4 + (n-2k)(n-k-1)^3 + k(n-1)^3] \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &= (n-1)^2 [3k^2 - (2n-1)k + n^2 - n] + [3k^4 - (7n-6)k^3 + (9n^2 - 15n + 6)k^2 \\ &\quad - (4n^3 - 9n^2 + 6n - 1)k + n^4 - 3n^3 + 3n^2 - n] - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &= 3k^4 - (7n-6)k^3 + (12n^2 - 21n + 9)k^2 - (6n^3 - 14n^2 + 10n - 2)k \\ &\quad + 2n^4 - 6n^3 + 6n^2 - 2n - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &= 2n^4 - 18n^3 + 82n^2 - 162n + 136 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n} 4m^2 \\ &\quad + (k-2)[3k^3 - (7n-12)k^2 + (12n^2 - 35n + 33)k - 6n^3 + 38n^2 - 80n + 68] \end{aligned}$$

Combining with the condition of the Theorem 2, we know that $(k-2)[3k^3 - (7n-12)k^2 + (12n^2 - 35n + 33)k - 6n^3 + 38n^2 - 80n + 68] \geq 0$. Since $2 \leq k < \frac{n}{2}$ is equivalent to $k \leq \frac{1}{2}(n-1)$. So what follows, we suppose $k \leq \frac{1}{2}(n-1)$. Let $q(x) = 3x^3 - (7n-12)x^2 + (12n^2 - 35n + 33)x - 6n^3 + 38n^2 - 80n + 68$ where $2 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2}(n-1)$. We divide the proof into following two parts.

Case 1: $(k-2)q(x) = 0$, we have $k = 2$ or $q(x) = 0$, It is easy to see that $q'(x) = 9x^2 - 2(7n-12)x + (12n^2 - 35n + 33)$ and the discriminant Δ of the equation $q'(x) = 0$ is $\Delta = 4(7n-12)^2 - 36(12n^2 - 35n + 33) = -4(59n^2 - 147n + 153) < 0 \forall n \geq 1$. Therefore $q'(x) > 0$ and $q(x)$ is strictly increasing in the interval $2 \leq x < \frac{1}{2}(n-1)$. Then $\max(q(x))$ is in the right endpoints of the domain of interval $[2, \frac{1}{2}(n-1)]$. Since k is an integer, we need to consider the parity of n . If n is even then $\max(q(x)) = q(\frac{1}{2}(n-2))$. By a simple calculation, we have

$$q(\frac{1}{2}(n-2)) = -\frac{1}{8}n(n-4)(11n-86) + 44 < 0, \forall n \geq 9$$

If n is odd, then $\max(q(x)) = q(\frac{1}{2}(n-1))$. By a simple calculation, we have

$$q(\frac{1}{2}(n-1)) = \frac{1}{8}[-11n^3 + 159n^2 - 421n + 433] < 0, \forall n \geq 12$$

In both the cases $q(x) < 0$. From the above analysis, we can see that $q(x) \neq 0$ for $2 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2}(n-1)$ and $n \geq 12$. Hence we only need to consider the case $k = 2$. If $k = 2$ then $S(G) \leq 2n^4 - 18n^3 + 82n^2 - 162n + 136 - \frac{(2n-3)}{n}4m^2$. If equality holds then $d_1 = d_2 = 2, d_3 = \dots = d_{n-2} = n-3, d_{n-1} = d_n = n-1$, which implies $G = K_2 \vee (2K_1 + K_{n-4})$. But in this case the equality $\sum_{v \in V(G)} d(v)^2 = \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{v \in V(G)} d(v) \right)^2$ does not holds.

Case 2: $(k-2)q(x) > 0$. In this case $k \geq 3$ and $q(x) = 3x^3 - (7n-12)x^2 + (12n^2 - 35n + 33)x - 6n^3 + 38n^2 - 80n + 68 > 0$. By **case 1**, we know that $q(x)$ is strictly increasing and $\max(q(x)) < 0$. Therefore for $3 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2}(n-1)$, we have $3x^3 - (7n-12)x^2 + (12n^2 - 35n + 33)x - 6n^3 + 38n^2 - 80n + 68 < 0$. A contradiction. Thus proof is complete. \square

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